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ABSTRACTS

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**Cross-Cancer Drug Repurposing of Ten Digestive Tract-Related Cancer Drugs
against Gastric Cancer Protein Targets**

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Abstract

Gastric cancer is the fifth most common cancer overall and the fourth most common cause of cancer-related deaths, worldwide. At the time of diagnosis, most patients are already in advanced stages due to the high challenges of early diagnosis. It takes a long time, is expensive, and is unsuccessful in developing a new cancer treatment medicine promptly. Drug repurposing, a technique for identifying novel therapeutic agents from currently used medications and medicinal substances, has the potential to produce clinical benefits more quickly and at a cheaper cost than de novo drug development. Drug repurposing is a growing area of research that gives an existing medicine a new purpose. This study investigates ten digestive tract-related (oral, esophageal, pancreatic, liver, small intestine, gall bladder, colon, rectum, kidney, bladder) anti-cancer drugs selected from standard drug databases. The potential drugs are identified by profiling the results of molecular docking and dynamics simulations of known drugs against validated gastric cancer targets. A virtual compound library is also constructed from known gastric cancer drugs and prioritized for these known gastric cancer targets. This study makes use of a variety of techniques to enable drug repurposing and lead identification of already existing non-gastric cancer drugs as well as novel compounds for gastric cancer.

Keywords: Gastric cancer, drug repurposing, molecular docking, molecular dynamics, virtual screening, lead identification

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